

DEVELOPMENT OF THE ACTIVITY OF ENTREPRENEURIAL SUBJECTS IN
ORGANIZING BUDGET AND CORPORATE PURCHASES IN OUR COUNTRY

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Annotation.

The process of organizing budget and corporate purchases varies depending on various factors, such as the advanced economic development of certain countries, their political structures and procurement regulations. At the same time, it is noteworthy that a number of developed countries are recognized for their effective and transparent procurement practices. This thesis presents the stages of organizing this process by a foreign state and its improvement in our country, as well as existing problems around the world.

Keywords: Budget, public procurement, budget contractors, corporate contractors, planning, competition.

As is known, the state needs various goods and services in the process of performing its functions. These needs are very important for the continuous and effective functioning of the public sector. However, no public sector is financially independent in meeting its needs, that is, if state organizations need a product, they cannot purchase it from any customer at any price without the participation of the responsible authorities. This is where the concept of public procurement comes into play. Public procurement is goods and services purchased by the government or state agencies at the expense of budget funds, produced in the country or abroad. Such purchases are made by the state in order to meet the state's own needs for population consumption and to create state reserves. When purchasing industrial goods and agricultural products produced in the country itself, the state sets certain prices.

As we have already said, public procurement is understood as the process of meeting the needs of state customers for goods (works, services) on a paid basis. State customers are divided into budget customers and corporate customers. State customers include:

1. State bodies (ministries, committees, agencies, higher state bodies)
2. Budgetary organizations (schools, MTT, healthcare) organizations
3. Recipients of

budget funds allocated for the implementation of procurement procedures;

We can include universities that do not have financial independence. They cover their activities from their own funds and budget funds. We also include theaters, publishing houses, the Ministry of Culture and Tourism and some libraries.

4. State trust funds.

Currently, there are 23 state trust funds in Uzbekistan. All of them carry out their needs in accordance with the principles of state procurement

5. Other funds established in budgetary organizations (development fund established in schools, director's fund) Corporate customers include:

1. State-owned enterprises; (100% state share)
2. Legal entities in whose authorized fund (authorized capital) the state share is 50 percent or more ;

3. Legal entities in whose authorized fund (authorized capital) the share of state-owned enterprises of this article and organizations in whose authorized fund the state share is 50 percent or more is 50 percent or more;

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Consequently, a significant part of the state budget expenditures is also carried out through state procurement, and such procurement directly affects the maintenance of budget balance. Therefore, ensuring its high efficiency in order to maintain the volume of state procurement at the most optimal level is an urgent issue. The solution to this issue is largely directly related to the introduction of modern information technologies into the public procurement process, which is one of the main directions of reforms being implemented in the field of public procurement today. The importance of this situation was also expressed by our esteemed President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who noted that “In the near future, it is necessary to create a single platform on the Internet for the implementation of all public procurements and the sale of state property. This will allow reducing budget expenditures, effectively managing state property and saving significant financial resources” [Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 3, 2021 No. PP-5171 “On additional measures to ensure the transparency and increase the efficiency of public procurement”. In addition, public procurement can stimulate the development of small businesses and innovative sectors of industry. The tasks of public procurement also include attracting more economic entities to the process to improve the competitive environment and encouraging local enterprises to produce quality products that meet international standards.

The current trend in organizing public procurement is the use of the Internet and modern information technologies in this process. The significant results of a number of important tasks set in this direction are also confirmed by the increased importance of using electronic trading in procurement processes. The introduction of electronic trading in the public procurement system has a number of advantages, which compensate for all the costs associated with its introduction. “The use of modern network technologies in organizing public procurement has a number of advantages over the traditional organization of procurement based on paper document circulation.

Even with the ideal organization of technologies such as “paper” organization of tender documents, publication of an announcement about the competition in the press, communication with suppliers of goods, collection of applications for participation in the competition, this process requires a lot of effort and time from the state customer. If corrections and clarifications are required to the documents, then all processes will have to be started almost from scratch. The introduction of Internet technologies will significantly increase the efficiency of the processes of preparation for the conduct of trade and competitive bidding, will lead to an increase in the number of suppliers of goods and services by simplifying participation in the competition and increasing its transparency.”¹

Public procurement procedures from April 22, 2021 [Urokov U.Yu. Public procurement. Textbook. T.: "Nihol print" OK, 2022. 200 p.]

Type of procurement For budget customers For corporate customers Deadline

Public procurement procedures from April 22, 2021²

Type of procurement		For budget customers	For corporate customers	Deadline
Direct (simplified selection)	Goods Work, services	0-25 BCA (base calculation amount)*	0-50 BCA	-

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-158 dated September 11, 2023 “On the Strategy “Uzbekistan - 2030”

² Urokov U.Yu. Public procurement. Textbook. T.: "Nihol print" OK, 2022. 200 p

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	per fiscal year	0-500 BCA	0-1000 BCA	
E-shop	Goods	0-2500 BCA	0-25000 BCA	48 hours
	Work, services	0-50 BCA	0-100 BCA	
Auction	Goods	0-6000 BCA	0-25000 BCA	5 business days
	Work, services	-	-	
Best offers selection	Goods	0-6000 BCA	0-25000 BCA	5 business days (2 business days discussion))
	Work, services	0-6000 BCA	0-25000 BCA	
Tender	Goods , Work, services	6000 BCA - ...	25000 BCA- ...	12-30 business days

In conclusion, it can be said that there are many other changes to expand public procurement, widely involve business entities in the sector, and ensure openness and freedom. A number of regulations are introduced into the procurement procedures, which significantly contribute to the organization of budget and corporate procurement by business entities.

